

RISK FACTORS FOR DEVELOPMENT OF NUTRITIONAL RICKETS IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of studies of the main risk factors for nutritional rickets in children. A retrospective review found that children not exposed to sunlight are more susceptible to rickets because sunlight is the main source of vitamin D. Limited exposure to sunlight is recognized as a significant risk factor for vitamin D deficiency. In addition, the study found that lower average birth weight highlights the complex relationship between body weight and rickets.*

Keywords: *rickets, nutritional rickets, vitamin D deficiency, hypocalcemia, hypophosphatemia.*

Introduction. Rickets is a disease caused by a temporary discrepancy between the needs of a growing organism for phosphorus and calcium and the insufficiency of the systems that ensure their delivery to the child's body. This is a metabolic disease with a predominant disturbance of phosphorus-calcium metabolism, as well as changes in the processes of lipid peroxidation, protein metabolism, micro- and macroelements. Rickets is observed mainly in children of the first three years of life, i.e. this is a disease of a growing organism. The leading role in the development of rickets is played by vitamin D deficiency, which occurs due to insufficient intake of vitamin D from food and its formation in the skin, and impaired metabolism of vitamin D in the body.

Calcium and phosphorus are two elements that are critical for proper bone growth. Concomitant physical illnesses associated with rickets typically persist throughout the child's childhood and adolescence and also cause acute life-threatening consequences that make rickets a significant health burden. Early diagnosis remains challenging due to the fact that the initial symptoms of rickets are not easy to notice. Children suffering from rickets often experience pallor, agitation, insomnia and increased sweating. The leading clinical signs of rickets are bone changes: deformation of the chest, protrusion of the costochondral junction (rachitic rosary), deformation of the lower extremities, deformation of the skull bones, frontal and parietal tubercles.

Malnutrition leading to muscular atrophy and increased susceptibility to infection are considered some examples of systemic symptoms of rickets. Multiple other risk factors have been linked to nutritional rickets, including exclusive breastfeeding, cow milk consumption, lack of sunlight exposure, malnutrition, and poor maternal nutritional status during pregnancy.

Materials and methods. Retrospective review using descriptive data from medical records of the 4-children's clinical hospital in Tashkent. The study was conducted among children of the Shaykhantokhur District of Tashkent. Data collection was carried out on hospitalized patients diagnosed with rickets from January 2024 to May 2024, inclusive. Eighty-four patients whose records showed they were suffering from rickets were included in the current study. The study included data from participants of both sexes and pediatric age groups (age group 6 months to 3 years). The following data were collected: age, sex, diagnosis, comorbidities, predisposing factors and radiological findings. In addition, biochemical test results (calcium, phosphorus, alkaline

phosphatase, vitamin D, parathyroid hormone, albumin, AST, ALT, and creatinine) were also collected from hospital records.

Results. Of the total number of patients (n=84), the majority were girls (63.10%) and the rest were boys (36.90%). The children studied were divided into three age groups: from 6 months to one year, accounting for 16.67%, from one year to 2 years, accounting for 25% of the total number of participants, and the remaining participants (58.33%) were from 2 to 3 years. During the survey, it was found that 72.81% of patients admitted that they were exposed to the sun 1-2 times a day, and 26.19% stated that they were not exposed to the sun. It is well known that children are at higher risk of nutritional rickets. Children have higher mineral requirements for proper bone growth and are more prone to diseases associated with vitamin D deficiency. It has been observed that children who are not exposed to sunlight are more susceptible to rickets since sunlight is the main source of vitamin D. Limited exposure to sunlight is found to be a significant risk factor for vitamin D deficiency, and the study found that 73.81% of participants had limited exposure to sunlight.

In addition, the birth weight and height of the patients were also documented and the mean birth weight was found to be 2.74 ± 2.23 kg (range 2.50 to 3.5 kg).

Patients were divided into four groups based on body mass index: 34% of participants were underweight, 33.33% were normal weight, 14.29% of participants were overweight, and the remaining participants (11.90%) were obese. The study showed that the majority of children with rickets were underweight (40.48%). In addition, the study found that lower average birth weight highlights the complex relationship between body weight and rickets. However, maintaining average body weight appears to be a protective factor even at a young age, highlighting the need to increase awareness among health care professionals about the benefits of average body weight in children.

According to laboratory studies, low levels of vitamin D were present in all participants with a mean of 16.91 ± 9.54 nmol/L, high levels of parathyroid hormone with an average of 79.39 ± 9.73 pmol/L, phosphate levels of 1.36 ± 1.67 mmol/l, alkaline phosphatase 205.52 ± 43.79 U/l. In terms of risk factors, 89.29% (n=75) of patients had a history of vitamin D deficiency in their family members, while 76.19% (n=64) of them suffered from malnutrition or lack of milk or dairy products. Exclusively breastfed infants were found to be 8.33% (n=7). Medications such as steroids or anticonvulsants were used by only 2.38% (n=2) of patients, while 16.67% (n=14) of them delivered prematurely or small for gestational age. The most common clinical manifestations in children were craniotables (53.57%); frontal tuberosities (16.67%); rachitic rosary (14.29%); parietal tuberosities (14.29%), thickened epiphysis (13.10%). Laboratory analysis revealed various abnormalities associated with nutritional rickets. Vitamin D deficiency is a known cause of calcium deficiency because it reduces the absorption of calcium from the intestines. Insufficient dietary calcium intake reduces calcium availability, leading to hypocalcemia. The body responds by producing parathyroid hormone, which regulates serum calcium levels by increasing 1α -hydroxylase activity in the kidneys, producing calcitriol from calcidiol. Calcitriol, in turn, enhances the absorption of calcium from the intestine. However, secondary hyperparathyroidism, caused by elevated levels of parathyroid hormone, leads to bone resorption and further limits calcium excretion from the kidneys, leading to hypophosphatemia and ultimately rickets.

Conclusions. Rickets is a preventable disease if it is caused by nutritional etiology. This study found that the children studied had limited exposure to sunlight, which is one of the key

factors causing vitamin D deficiency. In addition, it was noted that the children had low levels of calcium and vitamin D. Malnutrition had the highest risk ratio among children with rickets.

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